

Unveiling the emotional labor of overseas Filipino international teachers

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ABSTRACT

Emotional labor at work typically manifests through surface acting and deep acting. This phenomenological study examines the emotional labor experienced by 15 international Filipino teachers working in the United States, Saudi Arabia, and Thailand. Guided by self-determination theory (SDT), the research explores their reasons for teaching abroad, as well as the challenges they face and how they navigate them emotionally. A qualitative design was employed using semi-structured interviews and framed narratives. Each participant engaged in one individual interview and one focus group discussion. Data were analyzed using interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) to generate key themes. Findings show that deep acting involves emotional control, display of positive emotions, emotional exhaustion, experience of negative emotions, and emotional indifference toward self. In contrast, surface acting includes masking emotions, projecting artificial feelings, and withdrawal behaviors. The five major themes emerged as contributing factors to emotional labor: cultural adjustment, language barrier, professional challenges, limited support networks, and work-life balance. Coping strategies identified include emotional regulation, positive cognitive response, support from family and peers, and participation in recreational activities. These nuanced findings offer important insights for international teacher preparation, emotional well-being, and future research on cross-cultural educational contexts.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A significant number of educators have departed from the Philippines in recent years in pursuit of improved job prospects abroad. Ospina and Medina [1] indicate that numerous social, economic, and political factors have played a role in this trend. As a developing nation, the Philippines struggles to offer competitive salaries for its teachers. The combination of a high unemployment rate, inadequate wages, soaring inflation, and civil unrest has prompted many teachers to seek better economic and living conditions outside the country. Over the past decade, there has been an increase in job opportunities overseas that have attracted Filipino educators for various reasons, such as higher salaries, chances for professional advancement, and the opportunity to immerse themselves in different cultures. Those who have emigrated form a new cohort of teachers whose levels of job satisfaction, enthusiasm for work, and productivity have yet to be met while they remain in the country [2].

Emotional labor involves the deliberate regulation of one's emotional expressions to align with organizational norms and display rules, often requiring employees to implement effortful strategies (i.e., emotion regulation) to either suppress or fabricate emotions in professional settings [3], [4]. Emotional demands are the expectation to display or manage emotions in line with job requirements, with surface acting representing the regulation or faking of feelings to meet such role expectations—an essential component of emotional labor—which consequently leads to exhaustion and disengagement, reflecting psychological detachment from work [5]. Emotional labor can be both harmful and beneficial to employees, depending on which strategy is used (i.e., surface acting vs deep acting) [6]. Employees who smile at consumers and engage in deep acting genuinely have satisfaction in serving them. Conversely, staff engaging in surface acting do not experience authentic happiness when attending to consumers, although they continue to uphold the smiles conventionally anticipated by the organization. Consequently, various research have investigated the adverse impacts of surface acting in contrast to deep acting on individual outcomes. Deep acting is associated with enhanced well-being and promotes favorable customer relationships, while surface acting generally yields contrary effects.

Earlier studies have analyzed the two kinds of emotional labor as reactions. Research conducted by Wu *et al.* [7] demonstrated that emotional support, including encouragement and empathy, helps reduce burnout in environments characterized by substantial emotional assistance and minimal job demand/control. Furthermore, it was discovered that instrumental support, including assistance with problem-solving, also mitigates the adverse effects of burnout. Chang *et al.* [8] discovered that enhanced emotional support, like servant leadership, can foster intrinsic motivation in employees, for instance, psychological empowerment encourages individuals to practice deep acting in order to fulfill the performance expectations established by the organization and its leaders. This may subsequently result in increased psychological burnout, particularly for less capable individuals, as they endeavor to achieve the outcomes anticipated by the organization and their superiors. Mastracci and Adams [9] conducted a study on public officials from several cultural origins, indicating that in individualistic societies, particularly among North American samples, surface behaving dictated by display conventions led to increased burnout levels. Conversely, deep acting did not lead to heightened burnout under comparable conditions. In collectivist cultures originating from Asian samples, surface acting governed by display rules correlated with heightened burnout, whereas deep acting seemed to reduce burnout levels. This disparity is associated with public officials in collectivist societies being more sensitive to display regulations than those in individualistic settings. As stated by Horner *et al.* [10], teachers differ from those in other emotional labor roles, like positions in the service industry, as their interactions are more extended and ongoing with both students and families. In the classroom, teachers must serve both as experts in their subject area and as supporters of emotional growth. Additionally, teachers are anticipated to manage their emotional responses and interact with students and families according to established professional standards and protocols. A research study conducted in China outlined that the emotional labor experienced by preschool educators is marked by its extended duration, significant intensity, and variety in emotional exchanges [11].

Modesto research [12] on the sparse literature concerning Filipino teachers' perceptions of their professional identities and experiences indicated that these educators acknowledge and embrace their positions as integral members of their school communities. While the findings may not be universally applicable to all Filipino educators in the United States, the viewpoints of the participants were recorded and analyzed to highlight their unique identities, often neglected in current studies. Sumalinog [13] discovered that Filipino English educators encountered emotional obstacles, including profound homesickness for their families in the Philippines. They also confronted cultural hurdles, including language barriers stemming from diverse accents and various degrees of English ability among their students. Moreover, the educators encountered psychological difficulties characterized by burnout and sadness. Consequently, international instructors, particularly Filipinos, frequently encounter challenges that hinder a seamless teaching experience abroad. Macapagong *et al.* [14] examined educators' experiences, opportunities, and obstacles in international employment. Interviews with 10 participants identified four primary themes and 11 sub-themes, elucidating their challenges, coping mechanisms, learning experiences, and future planning while living in Arizona, USA. Filipino educators frequently encounter diverse opportunities abroad that pose problems requiring navigation. Adapting to a new setting is often a challenging endeavor, presenting obstacles for these educators.

Despite existing research detailing the experiences of teachers in other countries, Sumalinog [13] emphasized that there remain many more experiences to uncover, particularly in recent years where the trend of Filipino teachers working abroad is increasingly noticeable. This study has also acknowledged the crucial importance of context in influencing emotional labor as an area that requires further exploration, given that there are still few research examining instructors' emotional labor in foreign language classrooms. Moreover, few studies have examined how emotional labor is shaped by the unique sociocultural demands faced by Filipino teachers in the United States, Saudi Arabia, and Thailand, especially through a phenomenological

lens. These research gaps need to be delved into in order for aspiring international teachers to be well-aware. With the recent trend of teachers already serving the Department of Education and other learning institutions, yet still opted to teach abroad, indeed there are still more to look into. Hence, this endeavor aims to discover and disseminate information to prepare the teachers who think of going abroad.

The novelty of this paper lies in its application of self-determination theory (SDT) as a theoretical anchor to investigate the emotional labor of overseas Filipino international teachers. SDT posits that individuals are intrinsically motivated to engage in behaviors that fulfill their basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness [15]. These needs provide a valuable interpretive lens through which to understand the emotional strategies employed by teachers abroad. For instance, the use of deep acting—involving genuine emotional expression—aligns with the pursuit of autonomy and competence, as teachers consciously regulate their emotions in order to stay true to their professional values and develop mastery in cross-cultural settings. Similarly, their efforts to maintain positive relationships with students, parents, and colleagues reflect the need for relatedness. In contrast, surface acting—the masking or faking of emotions—may result from organizational constraints that suppress autonomy and create emotional dissonance.

The study further gains theoretical depth by positioning SDT alongside Hochschild's emotional labor framework, which distinguishes between surface and deep acting as responses to institutional display rules. While Hochschild's model explains how emotional labor is socially structured and often externally imposed, SDT complements it by emphasizing how individual motivation shapes the internal experience of that labor. By integrating these two perspectives, the study offers interdisciplinary insight into how emotional labor is both regulated by institutions and navigated through personal agency. Through its focus on Filipino teachers in three culturally distinct nations and the use of qualitative tools such as semi-structured interviews and framed narratives, the study provides original contributions to understanding emotional labor, coping strategies, and socio-professional adaptation in international educational contexts. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

- What are the types of emotional labor experienced by international Filipino teachers?
- What are the factors affecting the emotional labor experienced by international Filipino teachers?
- What coping strategies do they use in order to overcome those negative emotions?

By exploring the queries, this study aims to identify the reasons that drive Filipino teachers to pursue teaching positions overseas; examine the nature and manifestation of emotional labor (surface and deep acting) experienced in their host countries; explore the factors contributing to emotional strain or resilience; and document the coping strategies employed to navigate emotional challenges in foreign educational environments. These objectives seek to contribute to the growing body of research on emotional labor in international teaching contexts, and to provide prospective overseas educators and education policymakers with grounded, culturally relevant insights. This research may elucidate the particular motivations of these educators for residing and teaching overseas, as well as the experiences and challenges they encounter, so contributing to the expanding corpus of literature. This research facilitated an understanding of the future implications of the existing lifestyle and educational framework of overseas Filipino teachers. Therefore, it is significant to reveal the truths regarding the experiences of overseas Filipino educators.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study utilized a qualitative research style, specifically a phenomenological technique, to examine the emotional labor of Filipino educators deployed overseas. Phenomenology is appropriate for examining how individuals perceive and ascribe significance to their lived experiences. This method recognizes the presence of several subjective realities and aims to comprehend the phenomenon as viewed by those directly involved. The study sought to identify the emotional difficulties and coping mechanisms of Filipino educators in overseas contexts.

2.2. Population and samples

The participants consisted of 15 international Filipino teachers residing and working in three purposively selected countries: the United States, Saudi Arabia, and Thailand. These locations were chosen based on the researcher's prior knowledge of Filipino educators from the Zamboanga Peninsula who are employed in these regions. The inclusion criteria were as: i) Filipino citizen with single or dual citizenship; ii) home residence in the Zamboanga Peninsula; iii) currently employed as an elementary teacher overseas; iv) licensed professional teacher (LPT); v) with at least 3 years of teaching experience abroad; and vi) willingness to participate voluntarily. These criteria ensured that the participants shared similar cultural and professional backgrounds, enhancing the contextual richness and comparability of their responses. Focusing specifically on teachers from the Zamboanga Peninsula also allowed the researchers to explore how

regional identity which is shaped by shared language, cultural norms, and localized teaching practices, might influence the way emotional labor is experienced and expressed abroad. The region's strong sense of community, familial orientation, and adaptive resilience may provide unique insights into the coping strategies and emotional dynamics of its educators working overseas.

2.3. Data collection techniques

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and narrative frameworks to allow for in-depth exploration of participants' experiences. The interview guide, which was adapted and validated from the study of Jalilzadeh *et al.* [16] comprised nine open-ended questions designed in line with interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA). Interviews were conducted either one-on-one or in small focus group discussions, depending on participant preference and availability. These sessions were held via face-to-face meetings or virtual platforms such as Zoom and Google Meet, lasting approximately 1 hour each. During the interviews, participants were encouraged to share openly, and follow-up questions were posed to clarify and probe further into relevant issues. All sessions were recorded using audio or video devices, with the participants' prior consent. Participants were also informed that they could withdraw at any point and may be contacted again for follow-up if needed. Following the interviews, framed narratives were written by the researcher based on the participants' verbal accounts to represent their lived experiences in a coherent and contextualized form. These narratives were crafted to capture the essence of each participant's journey while maintaining confidentiality and thematic consistency across cases.

2.4. Data analysis

The recorded data were transcribed, organized, and analyzed using procedures consistent with IPA. The analysis involved identifying significant statements and key quotations from the interviews, which were then clustered into patterns and emergent themes. From these themes, a textual description was crafted to articulate what participants experienced. A corresponding structural description was then developed to describe the context and conditions that shaped those experiences. Finally, these descriptions were synthesized into a composite narrative to capture the essence of emotional labor as lived by the participants. Ethical protocols were rigorously observed throughout the study. Pseudonyms and coding systems were used to maintain anonymity and confidentiality. Participants were provided with both verbal and written informed consent, and all were briefed on the study's purpose, data usage, and their rights as participants.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research question identified themes regarding whether individuals engaged in a specific form of emotional labor benefited more from altering their felt emotions to match their displayed emotions, known as "deep acting", as opposed to "surface acting", which involves feigning emotions.

3.1. Emotional labor

Emotional labor involves the work, organization, and regulation required to display suitable and expected emotions in interactions with others [17]. Based on the participants responses, there were 8 themes that were generated, 5 themes fell under deep acting, and 3 themes under surface acting. Employees frequently perform emotional labor during interactions with their colleagues [18]. The authors demonstrated that several forms of emotional work among participants, including deep actors and non-actors, manifest in colleague relationships, each defined by distinct causes and outcomes.

3.1.1. Deep acting

Deep acting occurs more frequently in interactions among coworkers compared to surface acting [18]. It entails the congruence of interior emotions with external expressions to fulfill corporate standards. Consequently, it is linked to a reduction in adverse outcomes, including emotional discord and psychological stress. Among the participants, deep acting manifested in five key subthemes: emotional control, display of positive emotions, emotional exhaustion, experience of negative emotions, and emotional indifference toward self. As expressed by the participants:

"The Arab culture is insane... They're somehow violent if you have no control so you have to control your emotions." (Teacher 12)

"... I'm happily married with my American husband. I'm having a project in the Philippines, earning more than enough, I could be able to travel." (Teacher 10)

"The workload can be overwhelming at times, with lesson planning, grading, and extracurricular responsibilities often extending beyond school hours." (Teacher 3)

“There are times I feel lonely because I’m far from my family and I feel like I’m battling my own self of the overwhelming silence of being away from my love ones at that time.” (Teacher 2)
“One factor that I’m consider was being too doubtful of my self’s capability to teach foreign students.” (Teacher 3)

Deep acting represents a form of emotional work, requiring employees to be both motivated and equipped to invest resources in engaging in such demanding actions [19]. The degree of deep acting is likely to fluctuate among persons on a daily basis. The reactions of coworkers to the deep acting aimed towards them may also vary correspondingly. The dynamic model of emotional labor posits that the emotional labor exhibited by service workers can influence consumers’ immediate behaviors, including their interactions with the employee. Hong *et al.* [20] found that deep acting and expression of naturally felt emotions are positively associated with psychological capital (which includes optimism and resilience) and mental health.

3.1.2. Surface acting

Surface acting entails feigning emotions that are not authentically felt, accomplished by the deliberate use of verbal signals. The service agent simulates emotional responses that they may not genuinely experience. Diefendorff *et al.* [21] characterize surface acting as a type of emotional work in which individuals manage their emotional manifestations without altering their intrinsic feelings. Individuals feign or repress their authentic emotions to align with corporate standards, rather than experiencing the requisite feelings legitimately. Surface acting is manifested in three primary themes: masking emotions, projection of artificial emotions, and withdrawal behavior at work. Some of the responses were:

“I’m teaching first graders. Very challenging since, I used to teach higher grades in the Philippines. But I cannot let others see me struggle.” (Teacher 1)
“Yes, the emotional burden that I experienced was missing my parents (they are old so I am afraid of what will happen, and I am far), but others thought that I’m fun and strong yet faking it.” (Teacher 1)
“When I started teaching, I started missing my family back in the Philippines or shall we say I’m experiencing my first homesick.” (Teacher 9)

Although the term “emotional labor” was unfamiliar to many participants, their reflections clearly indicated conscious attempts to manage and suppress emotional states as part of their daily work. These efforts frequently led to a different kind of emotional exhaustion, characterized not by internal effort (as in deep acting) but by the strain of emotional dissonance—the gap between felt and expressed emotion. As observed in Sumalinog study [13], emotional regulation is a constant in the lived experiences of Filipino teachers abroad. Similarly, Auger and Formentin [22] found that surface acting often triggers emotional burnout in educators who must appear emotionally available to students while suppressing their own distress.

3.2. Factors affecting the emotional labor

Based on the participants responses, there were five themes that were generated from the second research question. This includes cultural adjustment, language barrier, professional challenges, isolation support from networks, and work-life balance. Some of the participants’ responses on the themes generated were as:

“Sometimes as at work, being misunderstood by other workmates. Different culture, different understanding and level of sensitivity.” (Teacher 2)
“Communicating in a language that is not your native tongue can be stressful and exhausting. Misunderstandings and difficulties in expressing yourself can occur frequently.” (Teacher 8)
“The pressure to perform well at my workplace. The demand of the job is a big factor when it comes to emotional labor. Also, the demand from parents, demand from the administrators as well.” (Teacher 5)
“...Professional expectations, student behavior and classroom management, performance pressure, balancing multiple roles are also factors I can tell that adds on to our burdens.” (Teacher 6)
“Being far from friends can make you feel isolated, especially during difficult times. The support system you rely on is not immediately available.” (Teacher 8)
“The only pressure of my work is that we have one Saturday that we have to come to school and discuss everything that needs to resolve or take action in our teaching, weekly plans, strategies, behavior and more.” (Teacher 10)

As presented in the responses, there are factors that contribute to the emotional labor being experienced by international Filipino teachers. This aligns with some results from the research conducted by Jalilzadeh *et al.* [16], which revealed that various personal, interpersonal, work-related, and institutional as well as professional elements can contribute to emotional labor. Furthermore, Sumalinog [13] study confirms that Filipino teachers abroad faced emotional, cultural, and psychological challenges. Additionally, a key factor that teachers reported as a source of stress was the “lack of administrative support” in dealing with what they perceived as an increase in their emotional labor. School administrators’ support may help reduce teachers’ allostatic load [23]. In an integrative review of teacher burnout in the Chinese context: “teachers in China face multiple unique stressors, particularly due to culturally ingrained high expectations on teachers, systemic pressure to perform, and job demands. Personal and organizational resources (e.g., social support, school climate) play a critical role in mitigating burnout” [24]. Filipino participants’ frustrations over administrative gaps (as cited in Teacher 10’s response) find resonance here.

3.3. Coping strategies

From the second research question, four key coping strategies emerged: emotional regulation, positive cognitive response, family support, and engagement in recreational activities. These strategies can be meaningfully categorized under the three basic psychological needs defined by SDT: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The relationship between emotional labor types and SDT needs is illustrated in Figure 1, which maps autonomy, competence, and relatedness onto deep and surface acting mechanisms used by international Filipino teachers.

The figure presents a conceptual framework diagram that demonstrates the incorporation of SDT into various sorts of emotional labor. The model correlates three fundamental psychological requirements of SDT—autonomy, competence, and relatedness—with forms of emotional labor (deep acting and surface acting), delineating the coping methods pertinent to each SDT domain as encountered by foreign Filipino educators.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework illustrating the application of SDT

Coping strategies that support autonomy involve practices that allow teachers to independently manage and regulate their emotional states. Emotion regulation, for instance, is a vital self-directed skill that influences individuals’ physical and psychological well-being, daily functioning, and quality of life [25]. It includes techniques such as reinterpreting negative experiences, redirecting focus toward calming or uplifting thoughts, and managing emotional expressions. One participant emphasized the need for flexibility and resilience in emotionally taxing situations:

“If you have plans coming abroad not just as teacher or by any field, make sure that you must have the nerves of steel and a heart like an iron. Be flexible, allow yourself to learn and accept every good opportunity and always have more patience.” (Teacher 3)

Coping strategies that support competence involve cognitive reframing and goal-oriented behaviors that allow teachers to feel effective in navigating challenges. A positive cognitive response refers to the constructive interpretation of stressful events and has been shown to buffer the negative effects of stress. This includes positive self-talk, optimism, and reframing situations to foster a sense of efficacy. Literature suggests that positive cognitive reappraisal moderates the relationship between stressors and adverse outcomes, and is associated with resilience and well-being [26]. As one participant shared:

“Good thing that Thailand is an open country. You can do whatever you want as long as with moral and consideration of their law. That is the reason also that I was able to cope my emotional issues in this country that fast because of their lively and vibrant lifestyle here.” (Teacher 2)

These expressions suggest a capacity for self-determined behavior, indicating that competence is fostered when participants perceive their environment as manageable and conducive to emotional adjustment. Lastly, coping strategies that support relatedness are anchored in the presence of meaningful relationships, including emotional and social connections with family, friends, and coworkers. Family support played a crucial role in many participants’ coping processes, contributing significantly to their emotional stability and well-being.

“For me as a family woman, my coping to my burdens is by finding healthy outlets like going outside with family, every weekend we have a family bonding with kids and sometimes with my husband alone.” (Teacher 13)

In addition, engaging in recreational activities—such as sports, hobbies, and social interactions—offered participants social connectivity and emotional relief. These activities represent voluntary and enjoyable experiences that enhance psychological wellness through informal yet meaningful interaction:

“I learned different strategies to relax. I do exercise every day. I play basketball twice or thrice a week. I hang-out with some friends/colleagues. I go out of town sometimes.” (Teacher 3)

Stress management approaches can generally be categorized as problem-focused or emotion-focused coping. Studies support the effectiveness of problem-focused coping, where individuals actively address the root cause of their stress. For instance, teachers who implemented proactive strategies in response to student misbehavior experienced reduced burnout [8]. Furthermore, research confirms the pivotal role of social support, particularly from family, in promoting emotional resilience and mental health [27]. Research by Fancourt *et al.* [28] highlighted the therapeutic benefits of leisure activities, including arts, volunteering, sports, and community involvement, in improving overall well-being. Educators’ stress/burnout co-vary with colleagues’, underscoring the role of collegial support in stress reduction [29]. Lastly, Kariou *et al.* [30] found that gender (female majority in teaching), emotional labor strategies, and emotional demands are key antecedents of teacher burnout/exhaustion. This aligns with teacher 13’s testimony, where emotional labor is compounded by her roles as educator and family caretaker—reinforcing the need for relatedness-based coping. This mirrors the relational coping (relatedness in SDT) seen among Filipino teachers, particularly the role of family and community networks. Taken together, these strategies reflect how the fulfillment of autonomy, competence, and relatedness needs contributes to adaptive emotional coping among international Filipino teachers. Table 1 presents the emergent themes from participant narratives, mapped onto SDT domains of autonomy, competence, and relatedness. It illustrates how emotional labor experiences are aligned with psychological needs and coping mechanisms.

Table 1. Themes of emotional labor with participant quotes and corresponding SDT principles

Number	Theme	Participant quote	SDT principle
1	Emotional control	“You have to control your emotions.” (T12)	Autonomy
2	Display pf positive emotions	“I’m having a project... I could be able to travel.” (T10)	Competence
3	Emotional exhaustion	“The workload can be overwhelming...” (T3)	Competence
4	Experience of negative emotions	“I feel lonely... being away from my loved ones.” (T2)	Relatedness
5	Emotional indifference toward self	“Being too doubtful of my capability...” (T3)	Competence
6	Masking emotions	“But I cannot let others see me struggle.” (T1)	Autonomy
7	Projection of artificial emotions	“Others thought that I’m fun and strong yet faking it.” (T1)	Relatedness
8	Withdrawal behavior	“I’m experiencing my first homesick.” (T9)	Relatedness
9	Cultural adjustment	“Different culture, different understanding...” (T2)	Competence
10	Language barrier	“Communicating in a language... can be stressful.” (T8)	Competence
11	Professional challenger	“The pressure to perform well...” (T5)	Competence
12	Isolation from networks	“Being far from friends... support system not available.” (T8)	Relatedness
13	Work-life balance	“We have one Saturday... to discuss everything.” (T10)	Autonomy
14	Emotion regulation	“Be flexible... learn and accept every good opportunity.” (T3)	Autonomy
15	Positive cognitive response	“Thailand is an open country... vibrant lifestyle.” (T2)	Competence
16	Family support	“Every weekend we have a family bonding.” (T13)	Relatedness
17	Engagement in recreation	“I do exercise... I go out of town sometimes.” (T3)	Relatedness

The mapping of participant responses to SDT principles highlights how emotional labor among international Filipino teachers is regulated through self-driven motivation (autonomy), task efficacy

(competence), and social-emotional connectivity (relatedness). For instance, strategies like emotional control and reframing stress reflect autonomy and competence, while coping through family bonding and peer interactions underscores the centrality of relatedness in maintaining psychological well-being. These patterns reinforce the argument that addressing core psychological needs enhances resilience in emotionally demanding professional environments. In the post-COVID era, where hybrid learning, travel uncertainties, and intensified caregiving roles persist, emotional labor is likely to become more complex and multifaceted. Hence, teacher recruitment and deployment programs should incorporate intercultural training and emotional resilience-building modules to better equip Filipino educators with the psychological readiness to manage stress, adapt across diverse cultural contexts, and maintain occupational well-being abroad.

4. CONCLUSION

This research concludes that Filipino teachers abroad are undergoing both superficial acting and deep acting as forms of emotional labor. While it is worth to note that these workers show more experiences on deep acting which can be implied that they are putting effort into actual feeling and expressing their emotions. There are also factors that contribute to the emotional labor being experienced by international Filipino teachers. These elements were observed to originate from individual, relational, job-related, as well as organizational and professional encounters that could contribute to emotional labor. Along this line, notable coping strategies like emotional regulation, positive cognitive response, family and peers support, and engaging in recreational activities that these international Filipino teachers are applying and they are seen as effective strategies the participants used in order to overcome the negative emotions that they experienced.

However, the study has limitations. The limited sample size (15 participants), although suitable for a phenomenological methodology, may not adequately encapsulate the varied experiences of all Filipino educators employed overseas. The participants were exclusively sourced from three countries (United States, Saudi Arabia, and Thailand) potentially constraining the generalizability of the findings to other global teaching environments. Future study should encompass a wider and more diverse sample, considering geographic diversity and various educational levels (e.g., elementary, secondary, and tertiary). Quantitative or mixed-method methods may be utilized to assess the degree and influence of emotional labor on teacher well-being and job performance. Moreover, longitudinal studies could provide profound insights into the evolution of emotional labor over time and in reaction to alterations in institutional or cultural contexts. This elucidates the emotional labor experiences of Filipino teachers overseas, enhancing comprehension of the emotional demands in global teaching environments and underscoring the necessity for culturally attuned support structures for foreign educators.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

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O : Writing - Original Draft

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Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors state that they have no recognized financial conflicts of interest or personal connections that might have seemed to affect the findings presented in this paper.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The information that underpins the results of this research can be obtained by contacting the corresponding author [LOB]. This data includes details that may jeopardize the confidentiality of the research subjects, and therefore, it is not accessible to the public due to specific limitations.

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